

RESEARCH INTO VOCABULARY ACQUISITION AND THE EFFECT OF MULTIMEDIA

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Abstract

This article suggests that additional factors may have influenced whether multimedia supported vocabulary acquisition, but these factors have not been explored in the studies—for example, ESL and EFL contexts; whether or not translation was provided; students' learning culture, such as whether or not rote memorization was the preferred learning technique; students' age and language proficiency; different teaching approaches and task designs; the complexity of the new vocabulary; the length of the study, etc. It is clear that, in this case, when we try to isolate and focus on the role of technology-multimedia, it is very difficult to make sweeping statements about what does or does not support language acquisition.

Key words: ESL and EFL, vocabulary, multimedia, studies, language learners.

Hi Everyone,

Hope you're all doing great this time.

I actually felt upset and deeply hurt about what is happening between Samira and Malala.

Please tell me Educators, what is the purpose of giving Group or Pair work to students?

👉 First, to train students for getting values such as empathy, Socialization, unity and tolerance.

👉 Only from empathy, love emerges and collaboration becomes successful.

👉 This, we all teach our learners about this Value daily. However, we're people on first line to conduct accordingly to ethic we expect learners to get.

👉 I plead with my lovely sisters to treat one another as real sisters and remember we're all a family because family tights, bonds but never goes into conflict.

👉 Sisters, take time to think of what we mean to build as family but do not focus much on individualism.

After all, we all aren't perfect, that's why we must admit our imperfection, focus on what we can achieve together and go ahead.

Love you All ❤️

Thanking you

Personal computer capabilities developed to include multimedia: graphics, sound, and later, video; this enabled to development of CD-ROM multimedia language learning materials. Multimedia and, specifically, the effect of multimodal learning-that is, learning through different combinations of sight and/or sound-has been a focus of learning technologies researchers for decades. Most early research into the effect of multimedia learning materials on the acquisition of vocabulary and improvements in reading comprehension with English language learners took place in university contexts (see Chun & Plass, 1996, 1997, for an overview). In contrast, in K-12 contexts in the USA, early research focused more generally on the effect of multimedia on the development of L1 literacy. Nevertheless, computers became increasingly available in both ESL and EFL contexts, and by 2010, research into the effect of multimedia on primary and secondary school English language learners had begun to emerge.

For language learners, it has been suggested that processing new information in many modes at the same time can lead to excessive cognitive load (Sweller, 2005). In other words, if language learners, especially at lower levels of proficiency, need to process text, visuals, and audio/video information simultaneously, this may overload their working memory and I to a breakdown in comprehension (Abraham, 2008). Research in ESL and EFL contexts seems to both support and contradict these claims. Silverman and Hines (2009) carried out a study with pre-kindergarten, kindergarten, first-grade, and second-grade students in the USA and found gains in vocabulary acquisition via shared readings supported with multimedia, as opposed to traditional print-based shared readings. This research concluded that the judicious use of multimedia can support vocabulary acquisition and reading comprehension for ELLs-that is, when the information is presented in multiple modes simultaneously, for example text, visuals, and/or audio/video. Another US-based study investigated the effects of a multimedia web-based program called ESL. ReadingSmart on reading comprehension with 66 Hispanic secondary school ELLs, with students using the program for 45 minutes, three times a week, over a period of eight months (Cuellar de la Colina, Episcopo, Hollier, & Lavell 2009). The researchers found significant improvements in the ELLs' reading scores after the treatment, suggesting that the multimedia approach helped students develop their reading comprehension skills over a period of time. However, different findings were reported in an EFL context by Lin and Yu (2012). Thirty-two junior high school students in Taiwan used a cell phone MMS-based vocabulary learning program

during a period of four weeks. The program delivered nine new vocabulary words a week to the students via the cell phones in one of four modes:

1 via text only a word, its syntactic category, the Chinese translation, and an example sentence;

2 via text + audio-including pronunciation of the new word/sentence;

3 via text image-including an image representing the meaning of the word;

4 via text + audio + image-that is, via all three modes simultaneously.

Students evaluated the program very positively, but in post-tests, no significant difference was found between the effects of the different presentation modes on vocabulary acquisition. In other words, in this study for acquisition as providing the new vocabulary with multimedia support. a single mode-text, with a Chinese translation-was found to be as effective Nevertheless, another Taiwanese study did find differences in vocabulary grade EFL learners carried out by Lin and Tseng (2012) examined the acquisition depending on the mode of delivery. A study with seventh-effects of animated illustrations or videos on the acquisition of what were considered complex-that is, difficult to define-vocabulary words. This study compared the effects of three modes-text only, text and graphics, the different i the new vocal extremely does not supp purely on the Vocabulary The increase opened up Researchers phone to see and text and videos-on vocabulary acquisition, which was measured via both immediate and delayed post-tests. Of the three modes, the researchers found that video support was most effective in helping students retain the target vocabulary and suggested that video annotations should be more widely used by teachers to help their students learn challenging vocabulary. Another area that interests researchers is how captions with multimedia might support EFL students' vocabulary acquisition, as described in Spotlight Study-1.

Spotlight Study-1

A study with 32 13- to 14-year-old junior high school Chinese EFL students carried out by Lwo and Chia-Tzu Lin (2012) examined the use of captions to support learning in computer-animated vocabulary lessons based on two scientific articles. The students were divided into four groups based on their proficiency in English, and four caption types were investigated with each group: no captions, Chinese captions, English captions, and Chinese plus English captions. Post-tests and semi-structured interviews showed that the effect of captions depended on the students' L2 proficiency. Lower-proficiency students performed better with English and with Chinese plus English captions relative to

students with no captions. The researchers suggested that lower- proficiency students 'relied on graphics and animation as an important tool for understanding English sentences'

(Lwo & Chia-Tzu Lin, 2012, p. 188).

Studies with university students mirror the mixed results above, with some studies showing a positive effect for certain combinations of multimedia and other studies showing positive effects for the opposite combinations. Not only are the results for university-age young adults mixed, but in some cases, it has been found that multimedia glosses do not aid comprehension significantly (Ariew & Ercetin, 2004); others have found a negative correlation between reading comprehension and the use of pronunciation, audio, and video annotations (Sakar & Ercetin, 2005). Reviewing the studies in this chapter, one can conclude that additional factors may have influenced whether or not multimedia supported vocabulary acquisition but that these factors were not examined in the studies- for example, ESL versus EFL contexts; whether translation was provided; the educational culture of the students, such as whether rote memorization is a favored study technique; the age and language proficiency level of the students; the different instructional approaches and task design; the complexity of the new vocabulary; the length of the study, etc. What is clear is that it is extremely difficult to make sweeping statements about what supports or does not support language acquisition when we attempt to isolate and focus purely the role of technology-multimedia in this case.

Vocabulary and Cell Phones: SMS

The increasing ubiquity of mobile devices-especially cell phones-has opened up new avenues of research in the field of vocabulary acquisition. Researchers have been especially interested in the unique ability of the cell phone to send short chunks of content-such as vocabulary words or short sentences to students via SMS, as well as in the cell phone's potential for delivering content based on a student's geographical location via its GPS tracking function.

A study in Taiwan by Lu (2008) investigated the effectiveness of SMS messages on 30 EFL high school students' vocabulary acquisition. In one week, 15 students-half of the group-received a printed list of 14 target English/Chinese word pairs; the other half of the group received two target word pairs a day via SMS message. The following week, the two groups swapped the way they received a second set of 14-word pairs. Vocabulary tests administered at the end of each week showed vocabulary acquisition gains for the students in both groups; in addition, no significant differences were found in further post-treatment testing

three weeks later. This study therefore suggests that the delivery mode of the vocabulary-SMS messages versus paper-made no difference to vocabulary acquisition.

An Iranian study, also carried out with 30 EFL high school students, found very different results (Tabatabaei & Goojani, 2012). During a two-month period, the students received five or six words per class via SMS and wrote a sentence including each word to illustrate its meaning. A control group of 30 students carried out the same activity but received words written on paper. The SMS group significantly outperformed the control group on a vocabulary post-test; in addition, the experimental group and their teachers displayed positive attitudes towards the SMS approach to vocabulary learning.

Location-based vocabulary learning supported by mobile devices is another area that has been explored by researchers. Chen and Li (2010) described the design and prototype testing with EFL students of a context-aware vocabulary learning system called PCULS (Personalized Context-aware Ubiquitous Learning System). Via GPS tracking, or geotagging, mobile devices delivered English/Chinese word pairs to students-based vocabulary related to real-life situations would be far more meaningful on their location; the reasoning behind this was that context-specific and memorable for students. The system was trialed with 36 tenth-grade students at 12 different locations in a high school in Taiwan. Over a period of two weeks, half of the students-the experimental group-studied the English/Chinese word pairs via PCULS; the other half of the students the control group-studied the same word pairs without the technology. In post-treatment vocabulary tests, 94 percent of the experimental group showed gains in vocabulary learning compared to 67 percent of the control group. In addition, 72 percent of the experimental group expressed a preference for context-aware vocabulary learning support.

Activity-1

The mixed results found in the three SMS studies described above illustrate some of the caveats in research studies that we outlined in Chapter 3 and make it difficult to generalize about learning outcomes. For example, the studies take place over short time frames; they involve small groups of students; and they do not consider the importance of external factors, such as learners' ages, interests, proficiency levels, previous knowledge, and levels of motivation. Choose one of the studies above and consider how you could redesign it to make it more robust. Apart from taking into account the caveats, consider also what theoretical

perspective you would take and consider whether you might collect qualitative and/or quantitative data.

Perhaps what this section on learning technologies and vocabulary acquisition via SMS illustrates is that learning is best understood as a cultural practice arising from the complex interplay between actors-both students and teachers-tools, and sociocultural/sociohistorical contexts. It lends support to Hubbard's observation that the role of technology in language learning is 'most properly viewed not as computers teaching people, but as people teaching people through the medium of computers'.

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